

Web-Based Information System Design and Analysis in Several Fields

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Abstract—The current era of globalization shows the development of various technologies in various fields. One of them is the development of a web-based information system. Information systems are the result of human design and consist of various components within an organization to achieve a goal, namely to provide useful information [1]. Web-based information systems can be used in various ways, namely for marketing, quality control, warehousing management, etc. The purpose of this study is to see how a web-based information system can help to solve various problems that exist in each field effectively and efficiently. Web-based application design is done by using PHP as the programming language and MySQL as the database. The results of this journal research indicate that the warehousing management of CV. ABB is becoming better and more effective than before after the implementation of a web-based warehousing management information system, an information system with web-based applications can increase efficiency and minimize weaknesses in the existing information system at the Process Laboratory IV PT. X, and the marketing information system are expected to increase the number of users of the island tourism in Sungai Pisang.

Index Terms—*Web-based, PHP, MySQL, Information System.*

I. INTRODUCTION

THE life of every human being is inseparable from problems. A problem is something that is not in accordance with what is expected and needs to be resolved or found a solution. Various problems ranging from simple to complex are faced by every human being. Humans as creatures who have reason and mind continue to make various developments such as technological developments to solve various problems that exist in the world. The current era of globalization shows the development of various technologies in various fields. One of them is the development of a web-based information system.

Information systems are the result of human design and consist of various components within an organization to achieve a goal, which is to provide useful information [1]. Information on the information system is obtained through data collection. Data collection must be done properly to produce an appropriate information system.

Web-based information systems will improve the performance or performance of an industry. An effective and efficient web-based information system is obtained if the

analysis and design of the information system are carried out properly. Analysis and design of information systems is an important part of the process to produce a web-based information system that fits your needs. Web-based information systems that do not meet the needs will hamper the processes of an organization. The resulting web-based information system must be easy to understand by users so that the application of the web-based information system is good and the objectives of the information system design are achieved.

Various problems can be solved with a web-based information system. An effective and efficient web-based information system can be one of the keys to achieving optimal results in marketing, quality control, warehouse management, and other things.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter contains a discussion of material related to the analysis and design of information systems and discussion topics discussed

A. Analysis and Design of Information Systems

Anggraini and Zega define the system as a collection of several elements or elements that interact with each other to achieve a certain goal [1]. Another definition of the system is a group of elements that are integrated with the same intent to achieve a goal [5]. Meanwhile, information can be defined as the result of data processing that has a certain value or meaning. Based on the definitions of these two words, Leitch and Davis define an information system as a system that connects the needs of daily transaction processing, operations support, management activities, and strategies within an organization to provide the required reports, both for internal and external purposes [1].

Information system analysis and design are used to understand what people need to be able to systematically analyze data flows, store data, process or modify data, and output information in a given context. Systems analysis and design seek to design, analyze, and implement improvements to an organization's computerized information system that is a means for users to carry out the functions of an organization. Information system analysis and design are used to create and manage information systems in performing their basic business functions. There are many approaches to systems analysis and basically, all of them have the same goal of understanding a complex system and then modifying it in some way. The result of the modification can be a new

subsystem or something else. The main goal is to improve organizational systems through the application of the software that can help employees achieve their main business tasks easily and efficiently. Ideally, the analysis stage to the design of the information system is starting from the old system, the proposed system, and the new system design [7].

Analysis and design of information systems must pay attention to various aspects so those information systems can run optimally. One aspect that needs to be considered is security. The security of an information system is important because if an information system has weak security, it will disappoint the user because the weak security will allow for privacy data leaks. In addition, weak security will also make information systems vulnerable to viruses such as viruses that can result in operating failures on an information system [6].

One aspect needed by the organization is an information system. The level of effectiveness and efficiency of information systems is a representation of the level of performance of an organization. Information systems must be able to support the organization in carrying out its functions [1].

B. Concept of Information System Development

The information system consists of two parts of users, namely end-users and management. Both users can influence the development or change in the scope of information. The development of information systems in an organization can be in the form of making information systems based on changes in the needs of information system users or due to new policies from the management. The form of information system development can be in the form of part or all of the information system depending on user needs or the policies that apply to the information system. The development of information systems is usually based on a reason such as to form an integrated system, to achieve system management efficiency, to support management decisions, and other reasons [7].

Forms of information system development can include [7]

1. Transformation of the old manual system to a new computer-based system.
2. Migration of the old system to the new environment with a different platform.
3. Fix and complete the shortcomings of the old system.
4. System reengineering.

C. Database

A database is a collection of data that is integrated, organized, and stored in a way so that can be retrieved easily. Another definition is that the database is a collection of data that is processed computerized into a piece of information that is interconnected and organized and can be obtained quickly and easily. Databases have several functions. The main function of a database is to provide information to its users. The database is an information system has several functions, namely a place to store data and information and a tool to process data and provide reports related to stored data or information. The data contained in the database must be

logically integrated [1].

A good database design should minimize data repetition and achieve data independence. Repetition of data is storing the same data in several different files. Data independence can be achieved by placing data specifications in tables and directories that are physically separate from the program. The use of a flexible and integrated database produces several benefits, namely increasing data accuracy, supporting transaction processing, data can be used simultaneously, reducing data repetition, maintaining data standards, increasing data security, meeting organizational data needs, and maintaining data integrity [1].

D. Data Flow Diagram Program (DFD)

According to Hartono DFD is a diagram that describes the flow of data in a system using symbol notation. DFD can also show the relationship between system components. Symbols are used to make it easier for readers to see differences between processes, and data storage [4].

E. Data Dictionary

The data dictionary is a collection of data and factual information from an information system following the needs [6]. The data dictionary stores the user name, the types of access allowed, the data item, and the name of the data item in the database to perform these checks. While the data dictionary can store the size and type of data items, data item constraints, and item names in data integrity checks [4].

F. ERD

Entity Relationship Diagrams are used in documenting user requirements and in designing a logical database using company policies. ER contains a complete set of entities with a number of attributes and a number of related components. The symbol is divided into two symbols, namely: attributes, entities, relationships, and links. Attributes describe the purpose of the relationship or entity. Entity or entity is a collection of real or unreal objects where the data is stored, usually an entity is called a noun. A relationship is usually named with a verb and is a relationship that exists between a set of entities. Link is a liaison between entities with their relationships and attributes [4].

G. PHP7 dan MySQL

PHP is a programming language used in programming and web development [5]. Another definition is that PHP is a web programming language in the form of a script that can be integrated with HTM [2]. MySQL is a database management system that uses SQL commands. PHP and MySQL have some advantages and disadvantages. The disadvantages of PHP are that PHP has security weaknesses, PHP code can be read by everyone, and the coding cost is very expensive. While the advantages of PHP are that PHP can make the web dynamic, has an open-source nature. MySQL is an application package with PHP and other advantages. Then, the lack of MySQL is that the application is slightly susceptible to viruses, the program can only run on windows, lacks support for visual programming language connections, and other

shortcomings. While the advantages of MySQL are that it can detect errors on the client, interface with all applications, is more flexible than other databases, and other advantages [4].

III. DISCUSSION

This chapter contains discussions related to the journal Improvement of Warehousing Management Through the Implementation of Warehousing Information Systems at CV. ABB, Design of Quality Control Information System at Process Laboratory IV PT X, and Design of Mobile Web-Based Island Tourism Biduk Marketing Information System.

The problems faced by CV. ABB is related to warehousing management. Warehousing management at CV. ABB is still done manually, causing risks such as very high data manipulation because the manual recording is done by warehouse officers, fake receipts, no system to control spare parts in the warehouse, and loss of spare parts in the warehouse. This problem must be addressed immediately so as not to cause more losses. Therefore, to overcome these problems, research was carried out in the journal Improvement of Warehousing Management through the Implementation of Warehousing Information Systems at CV. ABB. This journal has a research objective, namely to solve warehousing management problems in CV. ABB by implementing a web-based warehouse management information system. This research begins with conducting interviews with managers and staff at CV. ABB to find out what problems the company is facing. Furthermore, the identification of problems is carried out so that the existing problems are clearer so that ways can be found to obtain solutions. Then, a literature study was carried out to get a theoretical and practical foundation that helps in problem-solving. After that, data collection as needed was carried out and it was found that the solution to the problems faced by CV. ABB is the design of information systems. After obtaining the solution, the next step is to follow up to solve the problem by applying the concept of analysis and design of information systems through PHP7 and MySQL applications so that a new system is produced in the form of a warehousing management information system. The warehousing management information system is very helpful in controlling the PIC requesting spare parts, checking the stock of spare parts in the warehouse and stock out which is used by finance to make purchase orders, controlling all spare parts in the warehouse including incoming and outgoing spare parts, spare part request reports, reports spare parts from suppliers, and help finance to make purchase orders and get approval from users to make the process more accountable and corporate. The results of this study indicate that the warehousing management of CV. ABB has become better and more effective than before after the implementation of a web-based warehousing management information system. The problems that previously existed can also be resolved with the company's management information system. This company management system should always be implemented and developed continuously to obtain an increasingly effective and efficient company management information system. The development of the information system in this journal can be

in the form of development based on suggestions in the journal, namely the STNK notification feature that will expire so that it can avoid fines due to late payments and the addition of a spare part price menu in the finance section to make it easier to order spare parts. par and the addition of a finance report menu to find out the details of the purchase and expenditure of spare parts [4].

Furthermore, the problems faced by the Process IV Laboratory of PT. X is related to quality control information systems. Quality control information system in Process Laboratory IV PT. X still uses spreadsheets so that most of the activities and evaluations are still run manually which can lead to a minimal level of information security, slow information flow, and the potential for fraud. This problem must be addressed immediately so as not to cause more losses. Therefore, to overcome these problems, research was carried out in the journal Design of Quality Control Information Systems at Process Laboratory IV PT X. This journal has a research objective, namely to design a more efficient quality control information system by implementing web-based applications. This research begins with a preliminary study conducted by conducting interviews and observing the actual system to understand the existing problems and the environment of the Process IV Laboratory of PT. X. Then, an analysis of the existing information system is carried out and the results of the analysis are used as the basis for designing supporting applications. Furthermore, information system design and web-based application design are carried out so that an information system with web-based applications is produced. The information system with this web-based application has higher security than the previous information system because the system design involves four actors, namely admin, operator 1, evaluation staff, and CCP operator. This results in various positive impacts such as the level of fraud such as manipulation can be minimized and looping activities are eliminated. Eliminated looping activities can improve the efficiency of information systems and reduce human errors and writing errors in data input. The positive things above show that information systems with web-based applications can increase efficiency and minimize weaknesses in existing information systems [1].

Finally, the problems faced by fishermen of island tourism are related to the marketing of island tourism buckets. The marketing strategy used is still a word-of-mouth marketing strategy. Such a marketing strategy is less effective in increasing the number of tourists who use their island tourism so that their business tends to be empty of users. The tourists prefer to use the services of tour and travel in Bungus even though the price of island tours is relatively cheap. Therefore, to overcome these problems, research was carried out in the journal Design of Mobile Web-Based Island Tourism Marketing Information Systems. This journal has a research objective, namely to design a mobile web-based information system to improve the marketing of the island's tourism island. This research begins with the needs analysis stage, which is to examine how an effective marketing system is for island tourism in the Banana River and also collect data as needed as

the basis for designing information systems so that information systems are made according to user-friendly needs. Furthermore, the stages of designing a database system according to marketing needs are carried out using MySQL. Then, the marketing information system design stage is carried out using the PHP programming language. Then, the validation stage or the marketing information system test stage is carried out, whether the marketing information system is following user needs and produces the expected output. Finally, the implementation stage is carried out. This mobile web-based marketing information system is expected to support marketing activities and increase users of island tourism in Sungai Pisang [3].

IV. CONCLUSION

The design of web-based information systems can help to solve various problems that exist in each field and increase the level of effectiveness and efficiency of existing information systems. This journal shows that the warehousing management of CV. ABB is becoming better and more effective than before after the implementation of a web-based warehousing management information system, an information system with web-based applications can increase efficiency and minimize weaknesses in the existing information system at the Process Laboratory IV PT. X, and the marketing information system is expected to increase the number of users of the island tourism in Sungai Pisang.

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